

3-Cyclohexyl-5-Arylidene-2-Thiohydantoins as Possible Anticonvulsants

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Some new 3-cyclohexyl-5-arylidene-2-thiohydantoins were synthesised by the condensation of 3-cyclohexyl-2-thiohydantoin with araldehydes. Eight of these compounds, when screened for anticonvulsant activity against maximal electroshock seizures and pentylenetetrazol-induced seizures in mice at a dose of 80 mg/kg were found to be inactive.

N-CYCLOHEXYL nitrobenzamides¹⁻³ have been shown to possess CNS depressant properties. Further, 2-thiohydantoins have been found to exhibit sedative, hypnotic and anticonvulsant properties⁴. More recently, 3-aryl-5-benzylidene derivatives of 2-thiohydantoin have been reported to display anticonvulsant activity^{5,6}. Encouraged by these observations, the authors synthesised the title thiohydantoins with the expectation that the presence of N-cyclohexyl moiety might confer a high order of anticonvulsant activity on them. These compounds have been prepared by condensation of 3-cyclohexyl-2-thiohydantoin with various aromatic aldehydes.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

3-Cyclohexyl-2-thiohydantoin: N-Cyclohexylthiocarbamoyl glycine⁷ (5 gm), 2N HCl (25 ml) and ethanol (20 ml) were refluxed for 3 hr on a steam bath. Subsequent distillation of ethanol from the reaction mixture left a solid residue which was recrystallised from ethylacetate-petroleum ether, m.p. 110°, ir frequency cm^{-1} : 1740 (C=O of 5-membered ring) [Found: N, 13.8%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{OS}$: N, 14.14%].

3-Cyclohexyl-5-arylidene-2-thiohydantoins: A mixture consisting of an araldehyde (0.01 mole), 3-cyclohexyl-2-thiohydantoin (0.01 mole), glacial acetic acid (5-10 ml), fused sodium acetate (2 g) and a drop of acetic anhydride was heated on a steam bath for 2-8 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice cold water (25-30 ml) with stirring when a precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether.

The compounds thus prepared were characterised by their sharp melting points, ir spectra and elemental analysis (Table 1).

TABLE 1—3-CYCLOHEXYL-5-ARYLIDENE-2-THIOHYDANTOINS*

Compound	R	m.p. °C
1.*	3-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	186
2.*	4-chlorophenyl	232
3.*	2-styryl	248-49
4.*	2-hydroxyphenyl	210-11
5.*	2-furyl	211
6.*	2-chlorophenyl	200
7.	4-methoxyphenyl	180
8.*	phenyl	162-64
9.	2-nitrophenyl	228-30
10.*	3-nitrophenyl	240

Yield ranged from 45-50%.

* Screened for anticonvulsant activity.

+ Showed ir bands at 1640-1650 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Compounds No. 1, 3 and 6 were analysed satisfactorily for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen.

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